

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: PPP1CC.**

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7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 ovary, or epithelial ovarian cancer. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and
20 catalytically available phosphatase target in epithelial ovarian cancer: PPP1CC.

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26 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
27 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.
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1 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
2 transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification
3 (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the
4 transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of
5 non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the
6 brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates
7 through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

8 Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and
9 therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome
10 differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved
11 broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully
12 complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific,
13 subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel
14 immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a phosphatase therapeutic target identified through
15 rigorous study of the ovarian tumor transcriptome - a phosphatase target that is up-regulated and
16 catalytically available: PPP1CC.

17 Results

18 **Figure 1:** PPP1CC is differentially expressed in ovarian cancer.

19 I. Primary tumors of the ovary from humans with epithelial ovarian cancer.

20 $n=3$ normal ovarian tissue

21 $n=8$ primary tumors (ovary; human)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_24_P386771	2.59E-02	-2.5482501	-3.86035	-0.99947988	PPP1CC	6309/40462	84.4

22 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal ovarian tissue and in primary
23 tumors of humans with epithelial ovarian cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of protein
24 phosphatase 1 catalytic subunit gamma, encoded by *PPP1CC* in epithelial ovarian cancer in humans
25 (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPP1CC changed more than nearly 85% of the human ovarian tumor
26 transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 40,462
27 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1CC messenger
28 RNA in ovarian tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of PPP1CC during transformation of the ovary.

Thus, we concluded from blind transcriptome study of one cohort it was likely that differential
expression of PPP1CC defined the transcriptional landscape of epithelial ovarian cancer in humans.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
molecule inhibitors of PPP1CC phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be
tested for efficacy in patients with epithelial ovarian cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective

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phosphatase inhibitors for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase and phosphatase targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction with standard chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).

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Methods

We utilized GSE124766 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with ovarian cancer, as compared to normal ovarian (along with GSE146556 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).